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CARPOS

Coachable Robot for Fruit
Picking Operations

D3 – Fruit Picking Action Identification and Skill Extraction from Visual Observation

Abstract:

This deliverable (D3) documents the methodologies and outcomes of the research conducted in the context of “**Fruit picking action identification and skill extraction from visual observation**” within the CARPOS project. The work is part of **Work Package 2 (Active Perception)** and focuses on enabling the robot to learn harvesting skills by observing human demonstrations. As the action is performed by a human hand, an in-hand RGB-D camera (i.e., a camera attached to the robot’s end-effector) is utilized to capture the configuration of the human hand, the contact points with the fruit, and the fruit’s geometry and pose. State-of-the-art computer vision methods were applied to detect and track these features in real-time, while active perception strategies were employed to mitigate occlusion issues. The recorded trajectories and interaction points were mapped into a robotic representation suitable for subsequent skill encoding (WP4). The results demonstrate the system’s reliability to identify the fruit-picking actions and extract the essential motion and contact patterns required for autonomous reproduction by the robotic gripper. This deliverable, therefore, provides a critical link between raw visual observation and the multimodal learning framework of the CARPOS project.

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Περίληψη στα Ελληνικά

Το παρόν έγγραφο αποτελεί παραδοτέο του έργου CARPOS. Αναφέρεται στην αναγνώριση δράσεων συγκομιδής φρούτων και στην εξαγωγή δεξιοτήτων μέσω οπτικής παρατήρησης. Συγκεκριμένα, η ερευνητική ομάδα του έργου CARPOS ανέπτυξε μια ολοκληρωμένη μεθοδολογία αντίληψης που βασίζεται σε κάμερα RGB-D, η οποία καταγράφει γεωμετρικά χαρακτηριστικά του φρούτου, τα λεγόμενα σημεία αναφοράς (keypoints) και τη στάση (πόζα) του ανθρώπινου χεριού κατά την εκτέλεση της εργασίας. Για τον σκοπό αυτό χρησιμοποιήθηκαν σύγχρονες μέθοδοι υπολογιστικής όρασης, όπως το YOLOv8-nano για ανίχνευση φρούτων και του MediaPipe Hands για την ανίχνευση χεριών, ενώ υλοποιήθηκαν μηχανισμοί βελτίωσης της ακρίβειας προσδιορισμού του πεδίου βάθους και ανακατασκευής 3D σημείων. Η μεθοδολογία εφαρμόστηκε και αξιολογήθηκε σε δύο χαρακτηριστικές καλλιέργειες, την ντομάτα και το φραγκόσυκο, οι οποίες παρουσιάζουν διαφορετικές γεωμετρικές και λειτουργικές απαιτήσεις. Παράλληλα, σχεδιάστηκε αναπαράσταση της λαβής (grasp pose) “ανθρώπινο χέρι” - “φρούτο συγκομιδής” ως σχετικός μετασχηματισμός μεταξύ τους, ο οποίος μπορεί να μεταφερθεί προς υλοποίηση και εκμάθηση στον ρομποτικό χειριστή μέσω μοντέλων DMPs. Τα αποτελέσματα της αξιολόγησης δείχνουν ότι το σύστημα μπορεί να επιτύχει υψηλή ακρίβεια τόσο στην ανίχνευση καρπών όσο και στον εντοπισμό σημείων-κλειδιών αυτών. Επιπλέον, η υλοποίηση σε πραγματικό χρόνο καθιστά το σύστημα κατάλληλο για ενσωμάτωση στον βρόχο ελέγχου του ρομπότ. Συνολικά, το παρόν παραδοτέο αποδεικνύει ότι η οπτική παρατήρηση είναι επαρκής για την εξαγωγή γεωμετρικά συνεπών και λειτουργικά χρήσιμων δεξιοτήτων, οι οποίες θα αξιοποιηθούν στα επόμενα Πακέτα Εργασίας για την εκμάθηση και αναπαραγωγή της διαδικασίας συγκομιδής.

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INTRODUCTION

1.1 General Introduction

The CARPOS project develops a coachable robotic system for fruit picking that can learn directly from farmers through visual and kinesthetic demonstrations. Unlike traditional approaches that rely on explicit programming of robotic trajectories, CARPOS leverages *Learning by Demonstration (LbD)* to capture the strategies and motion patterns used by experienced human fruit-pickers. This allows the robot to adapt for different fruit types and cultivation conditions, while reducing the deployment cost and complexity for end users.

Within this framework, visual observation plays a central role. A farmer's hand movement, the fruit's geometry, and the interaction between the two must be captured in sufficient detail to allow the robot to replicate the skill. The current deliverable focuses on this visual pathway: how the system perceives and interprets fruit picking demonstrations.

1.2 Objectives and Relation to Other Deliverables

The purpose of Deliverable D3 is to demonstrate the CARPOS system's ability to perceive and interpret human harvesting demonstrations. Specifically, it focuses on detecting and tracking both the fruit and the farmer's hand during a picking action, identifying keypoints, and constructing reference frames for each. From these representations, the system extracts the grasp pose that describes the spatial relationship between the fruit and the hand, and records the detachment trajectory that follows the grasp. Together, these elements capture the essential structure of the harvesting action in a form that can be used by the robot.

Deliverable D3 is closely connected to several other outputs of the project. It builds directly on D1, which defined user requirements, use cases, and KPIs, and complements D4, which develops control strategies for maintaining occlusion-free visual observation. The grasp pose and trajectory extracted here serve as critical inputs for D7, where skills are encoded and generalized, while also providing representations that will be refined in D5 and D6 through kinesthetic corrections and human-machine interfaces. In this way, D3 establishes the foundation for transforming raw visual input into structured knowledge that can be encoded, corrected, and ultimately executed by the robot.

1.3 Background

Fruit harvesting remains one of the most labor-intensive tasks in agriculture, as many crops—including tomatoes, prickly pears, peaches, and strawberries—still depend largely on manual picking. Human workers continuously adapt their grasp type and wrist motion to account for factors such as fruit size, ripeness, and the strength of its attachment to the plant. These adaptations are essential for ensuring efficiency while minimizing fruit damage during collection.

Common harvesting strategies reflect this adaptability. **Power grasps** are used when the palm and multiple fingers enclose larger fruits such as tomatoes, providing stability and strength.

Precision grasps involve the fingertips and thumb delicately pinching smaller or more fragile fruits to avoid bruising. In addition, workers often apply rotational and leverage motions, taking advantage of natural detachment zones in the peduncle or stem, which allows the fruit to separate more easily with minimal force. These actions are subtle and context-dependent. Farmers develop them through long experience, and reproducing them with robots requires careful observation and abstraction.

In robotics, fruit harvesting has traditionally been approached with pre-programmed trajectories, often combined with force thresholds. While effective in controlled conditions, these methods lack flexibility and fail when fruit geometry or plant posture changes. This rigidity is unsuitable for greenhouses or orchards, where variability is the rule rather than the exception. The Learning by Demonstration (LbD) paradigm provides an alternative: instead of manually coding trajectories, the robot watches human demonstrations and extracts the essential skill. For this to work, two key challenges must be addressed:

- **Perception** – the system must detect the fruit, track the human hand, and infer their interaction, even under occlusions or changing viewpoints.
- **Representation** – the observed action must be reduced to a compact, transferable form, such as a grasp pose (a rigid transform between fruit and hand) and a detachment trajectory.

Keypoint-based methods offer a natural solution. By focusing on a small, stable set of reference points on both the fruit and the hand, the system avoids the complexity of full-pose estimation while retaining the critical information needed for grasping. The resulting grasp pose serves as the knowledge extraction layer: it captures how a human chooses to grasp the fruit, and it provides the initialization for trajectory models such as Dynamic Movement Primitives (DMPs).

METHODOLOGY

2.1 Visual Sensing Setup

The visual perception module of CARPOS is based on an Intel RealSense D435 RGB-D camera, rigidly mounted near the flange of the UR10 manipulator on a Husky UGV mobile base. This in-hand configuration provides a consistent field of view of the fruit and the human hand during demonstrations, while minimizing occlusions from the wrist and end-effector.

Camera specifications.

The Intel RealSense D435 RGB-D camera was selected as the primary sensing device for capturing fruit and hand demonstrations. Its wide field of view supports operation in cluttered greenhouse scenes, while the short-range optimization ensures reliable depth measurements in the 25–60 cm range typical of fruit-picking tasks.

The vision module used in the system integrates both RGB and depth sensing to provide accurate perception during fruit picking. The RGB camera operates at a resolution of 1280×720 pixels at 30 frames per second, while the depth sensor delivers 1024×720 pixels at 30 frames per second.

Depth estimation is achieved through active stereo technology with an infrared (IR) projector, enabling reliable performance under varying lighting conditions. The sensor's field of view is approximately 87° horizontally and 58° vertically, offering wide coverage of the scene. Its working range spans from 0.2 to 10 meters, but it is specifically optimized for close-range harvesting tasks, with best performance in the 0.25–0.60 meter range where accurate fruit localization and grasping are critical.

Calibration and alignment

Intrinsic calibration is handled onboard by the camera firmware, while extrinsic calibration between the camera and the robot flange is computed via hand-eye calibration. Frame alignment between RGB and depth is performed using the RealSense SDK API¹, which also provides post-processing filters (spatial smoothing, temporal filtering, and hole filling) to improve depth map quality in cluttered greenhouse scenes.

Environment

Demonstrations are conducted in both controlled and realistic agricultural setups. Initial trials are performed on mock-up plants with plastic fruit to allow repeatable experiments under stable conditions. More advanced trials involve real tomato plants of the *Elpida* variety, cultivated in a greenhouse-like environment to replicate natural picking conditions. Whenever possible, lighting is controlled to ensure consistent image quality, but outdoor and semi-outdoor sessions are also performed to test the robustness of the perception pipeline under variable illumination and background clutter.

Performance

The perception stack was implemented to balance accuracy with runtime efficiency. The fruit detection model (YOLOv8-nano) was deployed on an NVIDIA RTX 4060 GPU, while MediaPipe Hands² was executed on the CPU. The models run sequentially to avoid resource contention yet still achieve real-time performance, with overall acquisition, inference, and postprocessing kept within a few tens of milliseconds per frame. The entire pipeline is embedded in a ROS node that initializes the RealSense camera and the models, while also providing flexible control: streaming of hand frames, fruit frames, or raw RGB-D images can be toggled on or off to prevent unnecessary system load. This allows detection to run on demand rather than continuously, minimizing resource consumption when perception is not required. Such runtime efficiency is critical, since

¹ <https://github.com/IntelRealSense/librealsense>

² MediaPipe Hands: On-device Real-time Hand Tracking, Fan Zhang, Valentin Bazarevsky, Andrey Vakunov, Andrei Tkachenka, George Sung, Chuo-Ling Chang, Matthias Grundmann, arXiv:2006.10214 [cs.CV]

the perception outputs must integrate with the robot’s control loop running at 500 Hz, where any delays would compromise closed-loop responsiveness.

2.2 Fruit Detection and Pose Estimation

The identification of the target fruit is the first step in extracting a grasp pose from human demonstrations. For CARPOS, we use a lightweight YOLOv8-nano model³ running on GPU using CUDA, chosen for its ability to run in real time on embedded hardware while still providing high accuracy. The model is trained to return both bounding boxes around each fruit and a set of three keypoints that define a reference frame $\{F\}$ for the fruit (see Figure 1). In this deliverable we focus on two representative crops of the project’s use cases: **tomatoes and prickly pears**, which require different but structurally consistent keypoint definitions.

Figure 1: The identified keypoints used to define the tomato / Prickly pears reference frame $\{F\}$

Tomato Frame

For tomato perception, three keypoints are detected in the RGB image and projected into 3D using depth data: the fruit center (denoted as $C_t \in R^3$), the peduncle attachment (denoted as $P_t \in R^3$), and a secondary knee point along the peduncle (denoted as $K_t \in R^3$) (see Figure 1). The fruit’s geometric center is refined by projecting the detected “center” keypoint inward along the locally estimated surface normal, with the projection depth scaled to the fruit size derived from the bounding box. Using these keypoints the local reference frame $\{F\}$ is defined. More detailed, the **z-axis** of the fruit is aligned with the vector starting from C_t and pointing towards the direction opposite to P_t ; the **x-axis** direction is defined by projecting the vector from $C_t \rightarrow K_t$ to the null

³ <https://yolov8.com/>

space of z of $\{F\}$, and y -axis is obtained as the orthogonal complement, completing a right-handed coordinate system.

Prickly pears Frame

For defining the reference frame for prickly pears, an analogous procedure is followed with three adapted keypoints referred to the fruit center (denoted as $C_p \in R^3$), the attachment to the cactus pad (denoted as $A_p \in R^3$), and the distal top point (denoted as $T_p \in R^3$) as shown in Figure 1. Then, the frame is defined as follows: the z -axis is pointing from keypoint C_p to A_p ; the x -axis is defined by projecting the (denoted as $K_p \in R^3$) point on to the null space of z , and the y -axis is computed as the orthogonal complement, again forming a right-handed coordinate system.

Training datasets

For tomato detection, a dataset of 441 images with 1521 annotated instances (i.e. involving **1521 tomato fruits**) was created. For prickly pears, the dataset included 220 images with **1737 instances**. Annotation was performed using the Roboflow tool⁴, after which the datasets were exposed to Google Colab⁵ through the Roboflow API for training. All images were resized to 640×640 as part of preprocessing. **To improve robustness under varying illumination, augmentation was applied with changes in saturation, exposure, and brightness, expanding each dataset by roughly 50%**. The images were collected from three complementary sources: publicly available internet images, plants cultivated in the laboratory, and plants grown in greenhouse conditions. This ensured that the model was exposed to both controlled and natural variations in appearance, improving adaptability to field conditions.

Depth handling for small and unstable keypoints

For tomatoes, a challenge arises from the peduncle keypoints, which are small features with high variability in both shape and visibility. When localized slightly outside the true peduncle, depth sampling may mistakenly pick up background points, leading to large errors. To mitigate this, we apply a 20×20 pixel kernel filter around the detected peduncle keypoints and return the minimum depth value within that window. This ensures that depth is always measured on the foreground structure rather than the background.

Correcting the fruit center

The fruit center keypoint provided by the YOLO algorithm is an approximation and tends to lie on the fruit's visible surface rather than its true geometric center. To obtain a better estimate, we

⁴ <https://roboflow.com/>

⁵ <https://colab.google/>

analyze the local fruit surface around the center keypoint. A kernel is applied to collect surface points, from which we compute the average surface normal. The detected center point is then projected inward along this normal until it aligns with the actual centroid of the fruit volume. The projection distance is determined by estimating the fruit radius from the bounding box size, combined with the camera intrinsics to convert pixel dimensions into metric space. This way, the correction is not arbitrary but grounded in the true geometry of the fruit. The result is a stable and accurate center estimate, which significantly improves the robustness of the fruit frame and, in turn, the grasp pose computation. By combining YOLOv8 detection with these depth refinements, CARPOS achieves robust and geometrically meaningful fruit frames, even under occlusion and in cluttered greenhouse environments. The procedure for estimating the center of the fruit is depicted/presented in Figure 2. These frames serve as the anchor for defining the relative transform between fruit and hand, which is the core of the grasp pose extraction process.

Figure 2: Estimation of the center of the fruit

2.3 Hand Detection and Pose Estimation

Within CARPOS, the role of hand perception is to provide the bridge between human demonstration and robot skill extraction. The system must not only detect that a hand is present but also interpret how it approaches, contacts, and manipulates the fruit. For this reason, we employ MediaPipe Hand algorithm⁶, provided by Google AI, that implements a pretrained model as the underlying detection framework, chosen for its real-time performance and robustness in cluttered greenhouse scenes. An example of the results from Mediapipe is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Mediapipe hand detection results with 21 landmarks

⁶ <https://github.com/google-ai-edge/mediapipe/blob/master/docs/solutions/hands.md>

Although the model predicts a full set of 21 landmarks, we deliberately reduce this to three stable and functionally meaningful landmark points: the wrist ($W = p_a$), the thumb tip ($T = p_b$), and the base of the middle finger ($M = p_{ap}$) as shown in Figure 4, with $p_{ap} \triangleq \frac{p_{ac} + p_{ad}}{2}$. This minimal subset is sufficient to define the essential orientation of the hand during the grasp phase. From these landmarks, a consistent 3D hand frame is constructed with the wrist defining the origin, the z_h axis pointing inward the in-hand region, x_h pointing upwards and the y -axis is computed as the orthogonal complement, ensuring a right-handed system:

Figure 4: Visual detection of key points and the defined human hand frame $\{h\}$.

This yields a compact representation of the hand pose in space, suitable for computing the grasp pose as the transform between hand and fruit frame.

Relative wrist depth approach

Although tackled by Deliverable 4 of the project (“Control schemes for occlusion-free active perception”), in some cases, occlusions may occur. When the hand encloses a tomato cluster or presses against a prickly pear pad, the thumb and finger bases are often hidden from the depth camera, making their depth measurements unreliable. Since the stability of the grasp pose depends on accurate 3D localization, relying on per-landmark depth would introduce inconsistencies. To overcome this, CARPOS adopts a relative wrist depth strategy. The wrist is chosen as the anchor because it remains visible in nearly all picking demonstrations, even when the fingers are occluded by the fruit or leaves. We measure the absolute depth of the wrist directly from the RealSense depth image. MediaPipe provides relative depth offsets for each landmark with respect to the wrist. By combining these two sources of information, we reconstruct the depths of the thumb tip and middle finger base even in cases where their direct depth values are even in cases where their direct depth values are missing or corrupted due to occlusion.

The aforementioned wrist-anchored reconstruction ensures that as long as the wrist is visible, the full hand frame remains stable and consistent. It is particularly effective in the project’s two use

cases: tomato harvesting, where the farmer’s fingers often disappear behind dense clusters, and prickly pear harvesting, where protective grasp postures hide fingertips behind the fruit body. By designing the perception pipeline around wrist anchoring, CARPOS ensures that grasp poses can still be extracted reliably under the most challenging occlusion scenarios.

2.4 Grasp Pose and Hand Trajectory

To record how a human executes a fruit picking, the system must capture both the hand pose relative to the fruit. This is accomplished by defining two reference frames: one for the fruit, $\{F\}$, and one for the hand, $\{h\}$. These frames are constructed from a small set of keypoints (see Figures 1 and 4) extracted through visual observations by utilising the RGB-D camera mounted on the robot. Once the frames are identified and the fruit is grasped, the relative pose of the human hand with respect to the fruit defines the “**Grasp Pose**” and frame $\{h\}$ becomes the grasp frame $\{G\}$ as illustrated in Figure 5. It is important to note that the pose of frame $\{F\}$ can be easily expressed with respect to the tomato frame, in order to be, in turn, applied in any perceived tomato.

Figure 5: Grasp pose defined as the human hand posture relative to the target fruit reference frame

The **Grasp Pose** can be described and explicitly calculated as a homogeneous transformation, which compactly encodes both the orientation and the position of the human hand relative to the fruit and consequently relative to the base of the robot. This representation is compact, transferable, and can be used directly as the starting state for generating the robot’s grasping trajectory. During the demonstration of the harvesting process, the $\{G\}$ frame is continuously tracked and recorded over time. In this way, the $\{G\}$ frame serves as the starting configuration that can be extended into a full trajectory that describes how the fruit is detached from the plant. This trajectory captures the essential motions used by the farmer—such as twisting the fruit, pulling it straight, or levering it against its peduncle.

When several demonstrations of similar harvesting action are collected the corresponding trajectories are aligned and combined. By fusing them into a single, representative trajectory, the variability and uncertainty between demonstrations are reduced, and a more robust description

of the harvesting skill is obtained. This canonical motion preserves and generalizes the configuration of the grasp pose while extending it into the dynamic phase of detaching the fruit from the plant, providing the robot with a transferable template for skill execution. The fusing methods adopted and developed in CARPOS project are detailed in Deliverable D7 – “Multimodal skill encoding and generalization in fruit geometry variations”.

2.5 Mapping the human hand to the CARPOS Gripper

For the robot to reproduce a human-like motion, the grasp pose needs to be converted into a configuration the robotic gripper can perform. The CARPOS gripper was designed with a human-like structure i.e two flexible underactuated fingers, and a 1.d.o.f. actuated thumb. Instead of copying the human hand anatomically, the mapping follows functional roles: a) the human thumb tip matches the robot’s actuated thumb to apply opposing forces b) the palm center maps to the gripper’s inner surface for the main contact area and c) the human hand frame $\{h\}$ (see Figures 6, 4) to the TCP frame $\{e\}$ of the robot. The index and middle fingers correspond to the compliant fingers that naturally adapt to the fruit’s shape. When the human hand grasps a fruit (see Figure 5), its frame $\{h\}$ corresponds to the grasp frame $\{G\}$ and the relative grasp pose between $\{G\}$ and $\{F\}$ is calculated.

Figure 6: The CARPOS gripper and the corresponding mapping with the human hand

This mapping ensures that the geometric relationship captured by the grasp pose can be realized by the robotic hand, enabling the robot to replicate the essential features of the farmer’s grasp while accommodating the mechanical constraints of the gripper.

EVALUATION RESULTS

3.1 Results and Evaluation

The evaluation of the CARPOS perception framework was conducted against the **Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)** defined in Deliverable D1. To ensure a comprehensive assessment, multiple aspects of the perception pipeline were examined. These included the spatial accuracy of the 3D reconstruction process using the Intel RealSense D435 RGB-D camera, as well as the detection performance of models trained for tomato and prickly pear recognition. Tomatoes served as the primary test case for fruit keypoint estimation, while prickly pears were selected to validate the methodology on a crop with different geometry and harvesting challenges.

Hand perception was another critical component of the evaluation. The performance of the MediaPipe Hands model was assessed by combining evidence from published references, RealSense-based spatial analysis, and empirical experiments within the CARPOS setup. This allowed the framework to be tested not only on fruit detection but also on accurately tracking human hand configurations during harvesting demonstrations. Additionally, runtime performance was analyzed across acquisition, inference, and postprocessing stages, with particular focus on ensuring that the full perception pipeline operates within the time constraints required for real-time robotic control.

The results confirm the feasibility of extracting grasp poses directly from visual observations, demonstrating that the perception framework can provide reliable input for downstream modules. In particular, Deliverable D3 validates the ability to perform visual-only grasp pose extraction. Building on this, D4 will address robustness in scenarios involving occlusions and uncertainties, while D7 will use the extracted fruit and hand frames as the initialization for Dynamic Movement Primitives (DMPs). Together, these outcomes establish a solid foundation for subsequent project tasks and the practical deployment of the CARPOS system in real harvesting environments.

3.2 Spatial accuracy – RealSense D435

Spatial accuracy was evaluated by comparing the reconstructed 3D positions of fruit keypoints obtained from the RGBD Intel RealSense D435 depth sensor against ground-truth positions. Accuracy was quantified using Euclidean distances in millimeters, with metrics capturing both overall and axis-specific deviations. Several ground-truth measurements were recorded using a calibrated measurement board (see Figure 7), where the tomato was placed at a known reference position. The depth camera was mounted rigidly in a base to maintain consistent pose, ensuring fair comparison between reconstructed and true positions.

The results show a **Mean Euclidean Error of 13.1 mm**, representing the average deviation across all reconstructed points. The **Maximum Error of 42.7 mm** highlights the worst-case scenario, important for identifying potential outliers. In addition, **per-axis mean errors** were measured at **5.54 mm (X), 5.61 mm (Y), and 8.56 mm (Z)**. As expected, the depth (z-axis) produced larger errors, reflecting the known limitations and uncertainty of stereo-based depth sensing relative to

the lateral accuracy. These findings confirm both the strengths and the limitations of the sensor when applied to grasp pose estimation.

Figure 7: Spatial evaluation setup

Two plots were generated to visualize the results, **Per-Point 3D Euclidean Error** and 3D scatter plot. Per-Point 3D Euclidean Error shows the distance error (in millimeters) between each predicted and actual 3D point, depicted in Figure 8. The mean error was 13.1 mm, with a maximum error of 42.7 mm, indicating that the model achieves high spatial precision across most points. Errors remain low and consistent, with no significant outliers.

Figure 8: Per 3D point Euclidean error

The 3D scatter plot of Figure 9 displays both ground truth and predicted points in space. Each prediction is connected to its ground truth using a grey line, making the spatial deviations visually clear. The predicted points align closely with the true positions. Slight variation is visible in the x -axis, but still within acceptable bounds for practical use.

Figure 9: Ground-truth vs predicted 3D positions

The results confirm that the reconstructed keypoints align well with physical ground truth, with average deviations in the centimeter range and only occasional larger errors. These results confirm that the perception pipeline provides 3D accuracy within 1–2 cm, sufficient for stable grasp pose extraction for downstream grasping tasks, where tolerances on the order of one centimeter are typically sufficient to ensure successful robotic interaction with fruit.

3.3 Model Evaluation

The evaluation was conducted using the **Ultralytics YOLOv8** framework, which provides built-in tools for validating both object detection (bounding boxes) and keypoint estimation (pose). The model was evaluated on a validation set using the `model.val()` method, which computes key metrics such as precision, recall, mean average precision (mAP), and F1 score for both bounding boxes and keypoints. It also generates confusion matrices and precision–recall curves, offering a comprehensive view of model performance across different confidence thresholds. Bounding boxes are evaluated using IoU overlap, while keypoints are evaluated using the OKS (Object

Keypoint Similarity) metric. All evaluations follow COCO-style metrics, including OKS-based assessment for keypoints.

Dataset evaluation

First of all, dataset evaluation (see Figure 10) summarizes the spatial and size distribution of annotated bounding boxes. The top-left bar shows the total number of labeled instances for the single class “tomato”. The top-right panel overlays all bounding boxes, giving a sense of their relative shapes and aspect ratios. The bottom-left scatter heatmap illustrates the distribution of bounding box centers across the normalized image space (x vs. y): the points are spread relatively evenly, which indicates good coverage and low positional bias. The bottom-right plot shows the joint distribution of normalized bounding box widths and heights, revealing that most tomatoes fall within a mid-size range, though there is variation due to scale and distance in the images. Overall, this figure confirms that the dataset is balanced spatially and provides a diverse set of object scales for training and evaluation.

Figure 10: Dataset analysis tomato (left) and prickly pear (right)

Training Statistics

Training was carried out on Google Colab using the Ultralytics YOLOv8 framework, which provides built-in monitoring of learning dynamics. The loss curves (see Figure 11) for both bounding box regression and keypoint localization showed smooth convergence without instability, while the validation mAP curve was used to guide checkpoint selection. The absence of divergence between training and validation trends indicates that the model generalized well and exhibited no signs of overfitting. The framework also generated diagnostic plots during training, including precision, recall, and F1 metrics, which confirmed steady performance gains across epochs.

Figure 11: Training statistics for tomato (two top rows) and prickly pear (two bottom rows)

Aggregated results

Final validation was performed on a held-out set of 35 unseen images (134 annotated instances) for tomato and 17 images (91 instances) for prickly pear, with results summarized below. As mentioned, evaluating the detection model provides two sets of metrics: those based on bounding boxes and those based on keypoints. At first glance, several of these values appear identical, especially precision and recall (see Table 1). This outcome is expected, because a pose prediction can only be evaluated once a bounding box has been correctly matched to a ground-truth object. As a result, the true/false positives that drive precision–recall are shared between the two tasks, leading to overlapping curves (see figures 11, 12). The key difference lies in the mean Average Precision (mAP). Bounding box mAP captures how well the model localizes the fruit itself, while pose mAP uses Object Keypoint Similarity (OKS) to measure how accurately the individual keypoints are placed inside each box. This makes pose mAP a stricter criterion: it penalizes even small deviations in keypoint positions, whereas box mAP is satisfied as long as the bounding box sufficiently overlaps the object.

Table 1: Aggregated results

Metric	Tomato	Prickly Pear
Box Precision (BoxP)	0.936	0.977
Box Recall (BoxR)	0.989	0.967
Box mAP@0.5	0.991	0.987
Box mAP@0.5:0.95	0.951	0.907
Pose Precision (PoseP)	0.936	0.977
Pose Recall (PoseR)	0.989	0.967
Pose mAP@0.5	0.991	0.98
Pose mAP@0.5:0.95	0.974	0.97
Total Images	35	17
Total Instances	134	91
Mean Inference Speed	7.0 ms	6.3 ms

More detailed, the bounding box evaluation shows that the model is very accurate in detecting fruits (see Figures 12 & 13). The **Precision-Recall (PR) curve** stays high and steady across different thresholds, meaning the model makes very few false detections while still finding almost all the objects. The **F1 score curve** also stays consistently high, which tells us that precision and recall are well balanced no matter what confidence level is used. Looking at the numbers, the model reaches a **Box Precision of 0.936**, showing that nearly every predicted box is correct, and a **Box Recall of 0.989**, meaning it successfully detects almost every ground truth object. Taken together, these results confirm that the model is both reliable and robust when it comes to fruit detection.

Figure 12: Bounding Box evaluation metrics for tomato (Precision, Recall, F1 score)

Figure 13: Bounding Box evaluation metrics for prickly pear (Precision, Recall, F1 score)

Correspondingly, keypoint evaluation goes a step further than bounding box detection because it measures how accurately the model places individual landmarks. To this end, we use the **Object Keypoint Similarity (OKS)** metric, which adjusts for object size and how sensitive each keypoint is. For example, a small error on a fine detail like a tomato peduncle counts more than the same error on a larger part of the fruit. When looking at the **Precision-Recall and F1 curves**, the results for keypoints look almost identical to those for bounding boxes. This makes sense, since keypoints can only be predicted once the fruit has already been detected. As a result, **Pose Precision (0.936)** and **Pose Recall (0.989)** are the same as for bounding boxes. The real difference shows up in the **mAP@0.5:0.95** score (see Figure 14), where OKS pushes the

evaluation to be stricter. For **tomato**, the model scores **0.974**, slightly higher than the bounding box result (0.951). For **prickly pear**, the pose score reaches **0.970**, also surpassing the bounding box result (0.907). These results prove that the models can place landmarks very accurately, even under tighter evaluation conditions.

Figure 14 - Keypoint Detection evaluation

In summary, the PR and F1 curves primarily reflect the reliability of fruit detection, while the OKS-based evaluation provides a stricter and more informative measure of keypoint accuracy. When combined with the 3D spatial error analysis, these results confirm that the models can predict stable and geometrically meaningful landmarks suitable for grasp pose extraction. Both crops exhibit high accuracy and robustness across IoU thresholds, with the YOLOv8-nano models generalizing well to unseen validation images. In particular, the tomato model exceeds the project KPIs, ensuring sufficient precision for downstream grasp pose estimation and trajectory learning. Qualitative examples from the validation set (Figure 15) further illustrate this performance, showing close alignment between ground truth annotations and predicted detections.

3.4 Hand perception – MediaPipe Hands

For CARPOS, the **MediaPipe Hands** model was applied off-the-shelf, without retraining or fine-tuning on project-specific data. Its performance was assessed from three complementary perspectives:

- **Published references.** Prior studies provide baseline expectations for MediaPipe accuracy. In particular, [1] reported an average 3D error of **~3.1 mm** in controlled mechanical setups, while [2] validated MediaPipe Hands for clinical use, confirming its reliability under normal conditions and highlighting improvements when combined with depth information. However there are limitations under motion blur and occlusion, where some landmarks cannot be detected consistently [3].
- **Spatial accuracy from RealSense evaluation.** The spatial error analysis presented in Section 5.2, also contributes to validating hand perception. Since the hand and fruit frames are reconstructed in the same RealSense depth space, this error bound applies to the combined system, ensuring that grasp poses remain within the accuracy required by D1 (<20 mm mean error).
- **Empirical experiments.** In CARPOS demonstrations, the **wrist-anchored depth strategy** was observed to maintain stable hand frames even when the thumb tip or middle finger base were partially hidden behind the fruit. This confirms that MediaPipe Hands, combined with our reconstruction method, is sufficiently robust for extracting grasp poses during tomato and prickly pear picking demonstrations.

3.5 Real-time Performance

The runtime performance of the perception pipeline was evaluated to ensure compatibility with real-time robotic control. On the dedicated GPU (NVIDIA RTX 4060), the YOLOv8-nano fruit detection model achieved an average inference latency of **7.0 ms per image**, with an additional **8.1 ms for postprocessing** (decoding keypoints, projecting into 3D, and constructing fruit reference frames). Camera acquisition using the Intel RealSense D435 added ~5–6 ms per frame, resulting in an end-to-end cycle of **~20 ms per frame** under normal operation.

The **hand perception module (MediaPipe Hands)** was executed on the CPU, with typical processing times of **<10 ms per frame** when enabled. As the modules run sequentially, the combined end-to-end pipeline remains below the 33 ms budget required for 30 FPS operation, confirming that the system achieves **real-time perception**.

Importantly, the ROS integration allows perception to run on demand: streaming of fruit frames, hand frames, and raw RGB-D images can be toggled to avoid overloading the system. This ensures that computational resources are preserved during periods where detection is not required, while still providing **low-latency responses** when invoked .

The robot control loop at 500 Hz runs independently of the perception stack. However, the perception pipeline must supply updates at video rate (~30 FPS) with minimal delay, ensuring that control decisions always rely on fresh sensor input without lag.

These results demonstrate that the CARPOS perception framework is both accurate and efficient. The ability to sustain real-time performance is critical for integration with the robot’s control loop, which operates at **500 Hz**, where timely feedback is essential to maintain stable and precise motion during fruit-picking tasks.

The real time performance is summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: M Real time Performance evaluation

Component	Mean Latency (ms)
Camera acquisition	~5-6
YOLOv8-nano inference (GPU)	~6-8
MediaPipe Hands (CPU)	~8-10
Postprocessing	~5
End-to-end pipeline	~25-30

3.6 Summary

In summary, the evaluation demonstrates that the CARPOS perception framework meets the accuracy and robustness targets required for visual skill extraction. The tomato model exceeds all KPIs for detection and keypoint estimation, the RealSense camera provides spatial accuracy within 1-2 cm, and MediaPipe Hands—enhanced with the wrist-anchored strategy—offers stable hand frames even under occlusion. While prickly pear results remain placeholders, preliminary experiments confirm that the same methodology applies successfully to this crop. These findings establish a solid foundation for downstream work in D4, which will address occlusion handling, and in D7, which will encode the extracted grasp poses into transferable robotic skills.

DISCUSSION

The evaluation results confirm that the CARPOS perception framework provides a reliable basis for visual skill extraction, while also highlighting areas that require further development.

Strengths and limitations

The framework achieves strong performance across its main components. The tomato detection model exceeded all KPIs, demonstrating that a lightweight YOLOv8-nano can deliver high accuracy suitable for embedded deployment. The RealSense D435 provided spatial accuracy within 1–2 cm (mean error 13.1 mm), which is well below the typical fruit dimensions (tomato radius 25–40 mm, prickly pear length 60–100 mm). This ensures that reconstructed grasp poses are geometrically meaningful for robotic execution. The MediaPipe Hands module, supported by the wrist-anchored depth strategy, maintained stable hand frames even under partial occlusion. At the same time, certain limitations remain: **depth accuracy along the z-axis is more error-prone**, keypoints on small peduncles can still drift to background regions, and MediaPipe is sensitive to heavy occlusion or adverse lighting. However the high uncertainty along the depth axis is addressed by the active perception framework developed in CARPOS project, which involves the fusion of multiple demonstrations recorded from different view angles which are optimally selected (see **Deliverable 4 - Control schemes for occlusion-free active perception**).

Integration readiness

From an integration perspective, the framework is ready to provide reliable input to downstream tasks. The extracted fruit and hand frames are compact, repeatable, and transferable representations that can serve directly as foundation for **WP4 (Skill Encoding)**, where Dynamic Movement Primitives (DMPs) will generalize observed motions. The evaluation confirms that the spatial accuracy achieved is within the bounds specified in D1 (<20 mm mean error), giving confidence that the skill encoding process can proceed without requiring fundamental changes to the perception pipeline.

Risks and open challenges.

Despite these strengths, several open challenges remain. **Lighting variability** continues to affect both fruit detection and hand perception, especially in outdoor or semi-outdoor environments where shadows and highlights occur. **Occlusion** remains a possible risk, as both leaves and the demonstrator's hand can obscure critical fruit keypoints. While the wrist-anchored method mitigates some of these issues, robust active perception strategies developed in **D4** will be needed to systematically address them. Finally, **fruit variability** across cultivars and growth conditions

poses a challenge for generalization: additional training data and adaptive perception strategies may be required to ensure reliable performance beyond the current tomato and prickly pear datasets.

In summary, the CARPOS perception system has achieved its primary goal: enabling accurate extraction of fruit–hand interactions from visual observation. The framework has already met the KPI requirements defined in D1 for **fruit detection accuracy (KPI 1.1)**, **keypoint estimation accuracy (KPI 1.2)**, and **3D spatial accuracy (KPI 1.3)**, and it demonstrates readiness for integration with WP4. The identified risks—lighting, occlusion, and variability—are well understood and will guide the focus of upcoming work in D4 and beyond.

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